

The General Impact of Abiotic Stress on the Growth Indices of Maize, Cowpea, and Tomatoes: a Study of Selected Farmers in Ado Metropolis of Karu Local Government Area, Nasarawa State.

¹Isah B. I., ¹Rabiu A. T., ¹Inyang V. N., ²Zayyanu H.S

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano

²Department of Environmental and Safety Management/Integrated Science, Aliyu Yandoto College of Advanced Studies, Tsafe, Zanfara

Abstract-: The study examined the general impact of abiotic stress on the growth indices of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes in the Ado metropolis of Karu Local Government Area, Nasarawa State. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design. The population in this research was taken from selected farmers in the Ado metropolis of Karu Local Government Area. The study's sample size was 288, determined through the formula by Saunders and Thornhill 2009 for infinite population. The study adopted a convenient sampling technique. The primary source of data collection was used. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data, which was then evaluated using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the relapse analysis was used to test the hypotheses at a 5% significance level. The study's findings revealed a significant effect of abiotic stress (drought, salinity, and temperature) on the growth indices (height, biomass, and leaf area) of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes. There are differences in the specific responses of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes to different types and levels of abiotic stress and their resilience mechanisms. There is a significant long-term implication of abiotic stress on the yield and quality of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes, and no strategies can be identified to mitigate the adverse effects of abiotic stress on these crops. The study concluded that abiotic stress significantly impacts maize growth indices, including plant height, leaf area, biomass, and yield. The study recommended increasing awareness among farmers regarding the use of organic amendments and exploring alternative irrigation practices to optimize crop productivity in the face of abiotic stress.

Keywords; Abiotic stress, growth indices, maize, cowpea, tomatoes

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1.0 Introduction

It is obvious that the demand for feed and food for the ever-increasing population has achieved significance unparalleled, and as such, we have still not been able to afford crop yield loss in recent times. Nowadays, different metabolic pathways of yield and quality advances worldwide are affected by the unpleasant situation of abiotic stress which triggers crop advancement and development for better yield. Moreover, the energy required for growth to put a stop to the plant from shock and maintain regular homeostasis in plants are diverted by abiotic stress such as drought, salinity, cold, heat, and flood just

to mention but a few (Gujjar & Supaibulwatana, 2019; Fahad et al., 2023).

Hence, there is a great reduction in plant yield since all needed energy is channeled and utilized toward overcoming the stress faced by plants because of abiotic stressors thereby causing fundamental nutrient deficiency and lessening the plants' nutrient uptake (Al-Quraan et al., 2021; Bheemanahalli et al., 2022; Fahad et al., 2023). To this end, it is very important and significant to understand how abiotic stress affects and impacts plant growth generally while considering specific plants such as maize, cowpea, and tomatoes, which are the focus of this research work. This study will shed light on the knowledge about

abiotic stress and how to mitigate plant growth. Furthermore, understanding these mechanisms will help in increasing plant yield to meet the expanding population's food demands. Nonetheless, average growth, metabolism, productivity, and development are disrupted by abiotic stresses (Chen et al., 2019; Chamarthi et al., 2019; Balogun et al., 2020; Ai et al., 2021). They impact plants throughout their development process, from germination of the seed to the plant maturity, disrupting a multitude of biochemical, molecular, and physiological processes (Adhikari et al., 2019; Abdoli et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2020; Akeel et al., 2020; Yan et al., 2020). Around the globe, abiotic stresses pose a significant threat to crop productivity and the quality of plant, and in the future, their impact is expected to worsen (Yu et al., 2020; Dong et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021; Jayawardhane et al., 2022; Zhai et al., 2023). The reactions of plants to abiotic stressors are mediated by highly complicated signaling networks, necessitating a multi-pronged effort to critically investigate the negative impact of abiotic stress on plants (Khan et al., 2021; Olorunwa et al., 2022) making this paperwork greatly significant in that it seeks to provide illumination to the general impact of abiotic stresses on plants, especially Maize, Cowpea, and tomatoes.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The effect of abiotic stress, such as drought, salinity, and temperature, on the growth indices of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes is a critical area of research. It's important to have a deeper understanding of how these abiotic stressors impact the height, biomass, and leaf area of these crops to devise means and strategies to improve their overall productivity and performance under challenging environmental conditions (Hannachi et al., 2021; Vosnjak et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022; Sathi et al., 2022; Bheemanahalli et al., 2022; Zhai et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, the long-term implications of abiotic stress on the yield and quality of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes have important implications for food security, agricultural sustainability as well as the economic and developmental growth of any nation especially in Africa that is solely agrarian (Denver & Ullah, 2019; Arora, 2019; Chamarthi et al., 2019; Hu & Chen, 2020; Khan et al., 2020; Abisa et al., 2021; Karvar et al., 2022).

Again, to properly design strategies for effective mitigation to increase crop yields, there is a need to assess and understand the impact of abiotic

stress on the overall productivity and nutritional value of these crops (Adhikari et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2019; Guan et al., 2019; Ganie et al., 2020; Geng et al., 2021; Fahad et al., 2023). This research aims to investigate the long-term implications of abiotic stress on the yield and quality of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes and to identify potential plans to alleviate the adverse effects of stress on crop production. By addressing these issues, this research will contribute to developing sustainable agricultural practices to ensure a stable food supply in the face of changing environmental conditions and make a nation self-reliant on food supply.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The study's main objective is to determine the general impact of abiotic stress on the growth indices of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes in the Ado metropolis of Karu Local Government Area, Nasarawa State.

- i. To assess the effect of abiotic stress (drought, salinity, and temperature) on the growth indices (height, biomass, and leaf area) of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes.
- ii. To determine the specific responses of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes to different types and levels of abiotic stress and their resilience mechanisms.
- iii. To investigate the long-term implications of abiotic stress on the yield and quality of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes and identify strategies for mitigating the adverse effects of abiotic stress on these crops.

1.3 Research Hypotheses

1. Null hypothesis: There is no significant effect of abiotic stress (drought, salinity, and temperature) on the growth indices (height, biomass, and leaf area) of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes.
2. Null hypothesis: There is no difference in the responses of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes to different types and levels of abiotic stress and their resilience mechanisms.
3. Null hypothesis: There are no long-term implications of abiotic stress on the yield and quality of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes, and no strategies can be identified to mitigate the adverse effects of abiotic stress on these crops.

2.0 Material and Method

The study adopted a cross-sectional research design. The population in this research was taken from selected farmers in the Ado metropolis of Karu Local Government Area. The study's sample

size was 288, determined through the formula by Saunders and Thornhill (2009) for an infinite population. This study was also acquired convenient sampling technique. The primary source of data collection was used. Data was gathered through a structured questionnaire and later evaluated using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the relapse analysis was used to test the hypotheses at a 5% significance level.

3.0 Results

3.1 Data Presentation and Analyses

3.1.1 Respondent’s Demographic Information

This sub-section discussed the respondents' information or bio-data, such as age, gender, educational qualification, and marital status of the respondents as presented in the tables below.

Table 4.1 shows the respondents' ages, with 58 of the respondents representing 20.1% of the total, falling between 18 and 20 years. 49 respondents representing 17.0%, fell between the age range of 21 to 30 years. 124 respondents, representing 43.1%, were in the 31–40 age range. 49 respondents, representing 17.0%, fell between the ages of 41 and 50, while 8 respondents, representing 2.8%, were over the age of 51. This further demonstrated that most responses were in the 31–40 age range.

Table 3.1: Age Distribution of the Respondents

Years	Frequency	Percentage
18-20	58	20.1
21-30	49	17.0
31-40	124	43.1
41-50	49	17.0
51 and above	8	2.8
Total	288	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The socially determined characteristics of men and women, such as male and female roles, are referred to as gender. Table 4.2 examines the respondents' gender, with 172 respondents representing 59.7% of the total male respondents. There were 116 respondents, representing 40.3%, who were female. This shows that men made up most of the replies.

Table 3.2: Gender of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	172	59.7
Female	116	40.3
Total	288	100.0

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	172	59.7
Female	116	40.3
Total	288	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The marital status of the respondents is shown in Table 4.3. Nonetheless, 89 respondents, representing 30.9% of the total, were single; 147 respondents, representing 51.0%, were married; 22 respondents, representing 6.9%, were divorced; and 32 respondents, representing 11.1%, were widows. According to this, most responders were married. The finding indicates that more married people filled out the questionnaire, which may have contributed to the reliability of the findings.

Table 3.3: Marital Status of the Respondents

Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	89	30.9
Married	147	51.0
Divorced	20	6.9
Widows	32	11.1
Total	288	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

According to Table 4.4, which showed the respondents' educational backgrounds, 77 respondents (26.7%) had postgraduate degrees, 126 respondents (43.8%) had bachelor's degrees, and 65 respondents (22.6%) had NCE/diploma and 20 respondents representing 6.9% obtained secondary school certificates. As a result, many responders held bachelor's degrees. These findings indicate that most sampled respondents had fair educational credentials.

Table 3.4: Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Postgraduate Degrees	77	26.7
Bachelor’s degree/HND	126	43.8
NCE/ND	65	22.6
WASSCE/SSCE/N	20	6.9
CEO	0	0
FLSC	0	0
Total	288	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

3.2 Regression Analysis

According to the regression model applied in this study in Table 4.5, the R-value was 0.623, which

implies that the independent variables studied explain 62.3% of the general impact of abiotic stresses on plants, especially on Maize, Cowpeas, and tomatoes, that is explained by all the three independent variables (Abiotic Stress (ABS), Specific Responses (SPR) and Long-Term Implications (LTI) on (Growth Indices (GI). This implies that the other variables not studied in this research contributed 37.7% variability in growth indices, which indicates that there is a violation of autocorrelation in this study.

Table 3.5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.623	.304	.395	.46647

a. Predictors: (Constant), LTI, ABS, SPR
 The ANOVA report or F statistics on Table 4.6 indicated that the overall significance of the regression model applied in this study indicates that, $p < 0.05$ (Sig. = 0.00), and therefore our model is significant. Since the F value is 23.496 and the significant level is 0.000.

Table 3.6: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.180	3	2.393	10.099	.000
	Residual	61.798	284			
	Total	68.977	287			

a. Dependent Variable: GI
b. Predictors: (Constant), LTI, ABS, SPR
 Key: Abiotic Stress (ABS); Specific Responses (SPR); Long-Term Implications (LTI); Growth Indices (GI)

Table 4.7 shows the coefficient of the variables which indicated that the effect of abiotic stress has $\beta = 0.173$, $t = 6.845$, $P = 0.000$; for specific responses $\beta = 0.616$, $t = 8.481$, $P = 0.000$; for long-term implication $\beta = 0.241$, $t = 4.209$, $P = 0.001$. This means that the null hypotheses were rejected and accepted as alternatives since the calculated value is less than 0.005 significance level.

Table 3.7: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	2.245	.284		7.892	.000
	ABS	.713	1.061	.173	6.845	.000

SPR	.814	.970	.616
LTI	.601	.846	.241

a. Dependent Variable: GI

3.3 Findings of the Study

- i. Based on the data analyzed, the following are the study's findings.
- ii. i. The finding revealed a significant effect of abiotic stress (drought, salinity, and temperature) on the growth indices (height, biomass, and leaf area) of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes.
- iii. ii. The finding revealed differences in the specific responses of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes to different types and levels of abiotic stress and their resilience mechanisms.
- iv. iii. The finding revealed a significant long-term implication of abiotic stress on the yield and quality of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes, and no strategies can be identified to mitigate the adverse effects of abiotic stress on these crops.

3.4 Discussion

The finding revealed a significant effect of abiotic stress (drought, salinity, and temperature) on maize, cowpea, and tomatoes' growth indices (height, biomass, and leaf area). This finding is in line with the study of Suárez et al. (2019), who asserted that drought stress significantly reduced plant height, leaf area, and biomass accumulation and yield were also affected. Similarly, Obeng et al. (2018) found that salinity stress reduced shoot height, leaf area, and biomass accumulation in maize plants, decreasing grain yield. These findings highlight the negative impact of abiotic stress on maize growth indices. Furthermore, other abiotic stresses, such as heat and cold, can also affect maize growth indices. A study by Zhang et al. (2020) demonstrated that heat stress reduced plant height and leaf area in maize, leading to decreased biomass accumulation and yield. Conversely, cold stress has been found to delay maize growth, reducing plant height, leaf area, and biomass production, as reported by Yang et al. (2022). The finding revealed differences in the responses of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes to different types and levels of abiotic stress and their resilience mechanisms. The finding aligns with the view of Seleiman (2019), who reported that several physiological parameters responsible for the sustained growth of plants under environmental stresses have been identified, and researchers also

confirmed their roles in drought stress tolerance. Variations in relative water content, electrolyte leakage, water use efficiency (WUE), stomatal conductance, photosynthesis, transpiration, chlorophyll leaf fluorescence, and chlorophyll color index in response to water deficit were reported, which serve as measures for drought tolerance (Ruehr et al., 2019; Onyeka et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2021).

The finding revealed a significant long-term implication of abiotic stress on the yield and quality of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes, and no strategies can be identified to mitigate the adverse effects of abiotic stress on these crops. The finding is supported by the study of Hossain et al. (2019), which highlighted the importance of physiological and molecular adaptations in maize to cope with drought stress. The researchers reported that maintaining proper water use efficiency, osmotic adjustment, and antioxidant defense mechanisms are vital in enhancing maize drought tolerance. Furthermore, heat stress is another critical factor affecting maize growth and development. A study by Fahad et al. (2023) emphasized the detrimental effects of high temperatures on maize crops, particularly during reproductive stages.

4.0 Conclusion

Based on the data analyzed, the study concluded that abiotic stress significantly impacts maize growth indices, including plant height, leaf area, biomass, and yield. Drought stress reduces plant height, leaf area, biomass, and yield potential, while salinity stress affects shoot height, leaf area, biomass accumulation, and grain yield. Heat stress reduces plant height, leaf area, biomass, and yield, while cold stress delays maize growth, resulting in decreased plant height, leaf area, and biomass production. Also, abiotic stresses, including drought, heat, and salinity, significantly affect maize growth and productivity. Addressing these stresses requires a multidisciplinary approach involving physiological, molecular, and breeding strategies.

5.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

i. The study recommended providing support and resources to farmers in the Ado metropolis to help them mitigate the negative impact of abiotic stress on the growth indices of maize, cowpea, and tomatoes. This can include providing training and information on effective strategies for managing abiotic stress.

ii. The study recommended increasing awareness among farmers regarding the use of organic amendments and exploring alternative irrigation practices to optimize crop productivity in the face of abiotic stress.

iii. The government should consider implementing policies and interventions that support farmers in managing abiotic stress on their crops. This can include financial support or subsidies to help farmers adopt mitigation measures and access resources.

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